

Enhancing broadband vibration suppression of a cable conductor using graded metamaterials

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Abstract

Power transmission systems are essential for modern infrastructure, and their longevity and integrity are vital for ensuring uninterrupted power supply. They operate in harsh environments that can cause deterioration, making continuous monitoring essential. Among the major causes of fatigue and failure in transmission lines are aeolian vibration and vortex-induced vibrations induced by broadband wind excitation. These phenomena require robust control mechanisms operating across a wide frequency range. Vibration absorbers have been used to control vibration in power transmission lines. These devices act as notch filters, which limits their effectiveness to a restricted frequency range. Metamaterials have been designed and used in various configurations to improve vibration attenuation and mitigation. However, the bandgap of conventional metamaterials is relatively narrow, sometimes limiting their effectiveness. This paper proposes broadband vibration control in overhead transmission lines using metamaterial and graded metamaterial cable. The modal analysis approach is used to simulate the metamaterials and graded metamaterial cables, and a closed-form formulation describes the formation of bandgaps under the proposed configurations. The results obtained from the numerical model demonstrate that cable metamaterials are highly efficient in broadband vibration suppression and gap widening. Additionally, the tunable stopband of the metamaterials cable under aerodynamic and material damping shows the enhancement of the control under the damping effect. The metamaterials cable copes with the necessity of such broad control, and in their best configurations, the metamaterials reached from 86 to 99% on vibration reduction.

Keywords: Metamaterial; Rainbow metamaterial; Overhead transmission line; Metastructure design; Stranded cable.

1. Introduction

Energy transmission networks deteriorate during their lifetime due to environmental factors. Aeolian vibration, vortex-induced vibration, shedding, turbulence, thermal, and wind hazards are common phenomena associated with fretting fatigue and fatigue failure of power transmission conductors. Climate change (a global problem) is influencing temperatures, changing weather patterns, and disrupting rainfall, storms, and wind, which can affect the reliability of the transmission network [1]. Since power transmission lines play an important role in modern infrastructure, robust control systems are required to ensure stable and efficient electricity distribution across diverse and dynamic conditions. Furthermore, the control device facilitates predictive maintenance, contributing to a more resilient and sustainable power grid. Aeolian vibration is a wind excitation in broadband that compromises the system's integrity,

which should be minimised with vibration broadband control. The conductor has an intrinsic self-damping property that induces the attenuation of vibrations. This characteristic was assessed by Guerard et al.[2], who investigated four distinct conductors subjected to varying excitation conditions, including very low levels. The findings underscore the low level of self-damping and the necessity for an enhanced control system to address this issue effectively.

Castello and Matt [4] and Machado et al.[3] characterized and investigated the cable conductor vibration response influenced by aerodynamic damping and dissipation mechanism associated with the inner friction among the conductor's wires. Therefore, self-damping induces light control but is insufficient to avoid damage to the system. Dynamic absorbers are a typical passive control used to mitigate those undesired vibrations in an isolated manner. In a practical application, the experimental tests and monitoring of overhead transmission cables demand a series of equipment because of their higher altitude installation, combined with slender and long-length structures. Devices such as spacers, spacer dampers, and dampers, among others, are solutions installed on the conductor to attenuate undesired vibration.

The Stockbridge damper is a tuned mass damper (absorber) commonly used for vibration suppression in conductor cables. In general, the control operates up to two resonant frequencies simultaneously, and its effectiveness can be affected by the installation position on the conductor, apart from its overall characteristics [5, 6, 7]. Vaja et al.[8] designed an asymmetric Stockbridge damper that controls up to four resonant frequencies, and Bukhari et al. [9] investigated the performance of a moving damper for overhead transmission lines in an attempt to improve vibration attenuation. Recently, Kakou et al. [10] proposed a mobile robot vibration absorber capable of self-adjustment to better control performance. In [12, 11], the authors formulated and optimised several absorbers installed along the line but with no thorough analysis of the vibration attenuation efficacy. A review of the outlook of future development of the Stockbridge damper was published by Wang et al.[13]. Hence, using those absorbers is still the main practical for vibration control of overhead transmission lines because of the design, manufacture, and installation facility. Therefore, those controls operate in one specific tuned frequency and are efficient in vibration attenuation but not suppression.

The development of metamaterial for engineering applications has grown over the past decade, boosted by advances in the manufacturing process. Metamaterials offer a broad application in vibration control, from attenuating vibration to inducing isolation and mitigation of local frequency bands, known as bandgaps. Most designed metamaterials for vibration control are periodic structures with resonators distributed along the structure, producing good vibration attenuation within bandgap regions compared to the traditional dynamic absorber [14]. They also work for elastic waves of short and long wavelengths[15]. A comprehensive overview of metamaterials and their applications was published in [16, 17], specifically for vibration control by [18]. Local resonators are based on the concept of mechanical dynamic vibration absorbers (DVAs) [19, 21, 20]. Several researchers have explored the functionality and efficiency of locally resonant elastic-acoustic metamaterials on various structures. The theory of metamaterial beam designed for broadband vibration control was published in [21], and Dianlong et al. [22] explored the flexural vibration band gaps in Euler-Bernoulli beams with locally resonant structures with two degrees of freedom. The mechanism of bandgap formation in a beam was presented in Sugino et al.[23], and a general theory for bandgap estimation in locally resonant metastructures was published in [26]. Xiao et al.[24, 25] investigated the bandgap behaviour and the formation mechanisms of beams with periodically attached vibration absorbers and, in [27], the authors expanded on previous studies by introducing multiple periodic arrays of local resonators into a local resonators beam to explore

the broadband vibration attenuation. Zhong et al. [28] investigated the metamaterial I-Girder beam for vibration absorption of composite stayed bridges, and Singleton et al.[29] designed a resonator-based metamaterial for broadband control of transverse taut string vibration. Zhou et al. [30] explored the tunable flexural wave bandgaps in a prestressed elastic beam with periodic smart resonators.

Numerous approaches have been proposed to widen the bandgaps of metamaterials. In [31, 32], the authors used local resonators with multiple degrees of freedom. In [27, 33], they used multiple independent local resonators with single-degree-of-freedom. Internal couplings between neighbouring local resonators in conventional metamaterials to induce additional bandgaps were investigated in [34, 35]. Another interesting concept for achieving broadband vibration attenuation is the use of graded metastructures, which has its origin in optical [36], acoustic [37], ultrasonic [38], acoustic metasurfaces [79], and elastic [39] waves applications. A significant bandgap widening of locally resonant metamaterials can be improved from the typical periodic design using near-periodic, quasi-periodic or a-periodic approaches. Celli [40] proposed the graded metamaterial to improve vibration attenuation. It relies on the graded trap phenomenon and requires arrays of resonators with different characteristics, where each resonator type operates in a selected frequency. Hu et al.[41] presented the graded metamaterial beam approach, also investigated by [42, 43], which refers to the variation in the natural frequencies of the local resonators to achieve broadband vibration suppression. A study about architecture optimisation of graded metamaterial was explored in [44].

Structures attached with single- and multi-resonator were modelled by transfer matrix [45, 46], plane wave expansion [47], spectral element method [25, 35], modal analysis [48], among others. The modal analysis approach incorporates the modal parameter information and the dependence of the bandgap width on the number and spatial distribution of attachments in a finite structure. This approach implies simple formulation and only relies on the modal parameters of the primary structure, natural resonator frequency, and total mass ratio, yielding an analytical insight that is fast and accurate for design purposes. Sugino et al. [23] proposed an analytical solution based on the modal analysis of bandgap formation, where the authors managed to derive (in closed form) the expression for the bandgap edge frequencies using the single resonant frequency of the resonators and the ratio of the resonator mass to the primary structure mass. However, this theory is limited to a single resonator attached to undamped structures, such as string, rod, shaft, beam, membrane, and plate. El-Borgi et al.[48] present an extension of Sugino’s theory by adding multiple resonators that simultaneously operate in multi-frequencies. Despite numerous applications and models exploring vibration control on the cable conductor of overhead transmission lines, studies on the metamaterial and graded metamaterial cable exploring their dynamic response and the local broadband bandgap formation from single to multiple frequencies are still unheard of in the literature. To the best of our knowledge, this application remains unexplored and an open challenge to be addressed with new solutions for vibration control on cable conductors.

This paper proposes an innovative solution that employs a cable and graded metamaterials design for broadband vibration mitigation of cable conductors of overhead transmission lines. We use the modal analysis approach to model the metamaterials, motivated by the need to establish a simple mathematical method that is easily described, implements the cable model with low computational cost, and is accurate. Therefore, the main contribution of this paper is to extend the theory proposed by Sugino et al.[23] to design the metamaterial and graded metamaterial cable. Numerical applications demonstrate the local resonant bandgap formation in narrow and broad frequency bands aiming at the vibration suppression. The efficiency of the cable and graded metamaterial for bandgap widening,

related to the influence of aerodynamic and structural damping, is also investigated. To cope with the proposed control mechanism, a data-driven of the dynamic responses of a cable conductor ACSR Grosbeak is used to validate the plain cable model, which is then used to forecast its optimal broadband vibration mitigation configuration numerically. The results show a significant improvement in the dynamic control performance of the metamaterial cable under the effect of multi-frequency parametric excitation, offering a promising solution to mitigate the impact of aeolian vibration on overhead transmission systems.

Section 2 shows the resonators in single, multiple and graded configurations. Section 3 describes the formulation of the metamaterial cable conductor designed to perform local bandgap formation using single-degree-of-freedom resonators followed by the graded metamaterial. Section 4 presents the cable conductor metamaterial attached to the multiple-DOF formulation. Numerical results and discussion on the proposed methodology and the overall model validation are presented in Section 5. Concluding remarks are given in Section 6. Appendix A describes the cable's parameter estimation using the Bayesian Inference technique and Appendix B the spectral transfer matrix approach and wavenumber estimation.

2. Modal properties of the vibration resonators

Unlike phononic crystals that utilise Bragg scattering, metamaterials designed for periodic structures with local resonance can exhibit bandgaps at much longer wavelengths than the size of the structure's repeating units. This property enables these metamaterials to effectively attenuate low-frequency vibrations, guide waves, and perform filtering, among other applications. When employing the concept of metamaterials to control cable vibrations by inducing local bandgaps, the effectiveness of this approach is based on the characteristics of the bandgap formed through local resonance[80]. This approach is not restricted to wavelengths in the same order as the lattice spacing. That is, it can lie in the subwavelength regime whereby waves with wavelengths larger than that of the unit cell will be prohibited from propagation. While the formation of bandgaps is usually explained using wave-related arguments assuming continuous travelling waves and an infinitely repeated unit cell structure, this perspective doesn't fully apply to finite structures where the dynamic response depends on mode shapes. Therefore, this study uses a modal analysis approach to analyse and design finite metamaterial cables with local resonance, treating them as one-dimensional waveguides. We adopt and validate the concept of infinite absorbers on the finite structure to gain analytical insight, following the one proposed in [23]. We assume that the resonators are attached in line with a lattice constant ($l_{cell}=L/10$ m) smaller than the flexural wavelength, $\lambda = 2\pi/kn$, with cable wavenumber [3] $kn = \pm \left(-\frac{T}{2EI} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{T}{2EI}\right)^2 + \frac{\rho A\omega^2}{EI}} \right)^{1/2}$, of the host cable conductor at the resonance frequency of 9.51 and 15.48 Hz. Therefore, the ratio l_{cell}/λ for both frequencies are 0.4 and 0.6, respectively.

The metamaterial cable contains S -number of resonators placed in a subdomain, where for $\Delta L_j = \int_{L_j} dL$ is the length of the subdomain L_j . In all cable metamaterial designs, the spring coefficient of each resonator is assumed to be the same. In contrast, the resonator mass is defined by $m_p = \epsilon m \Delta L$ [23], where the mass ratio is $\epsilon = \sum_{p=1}^S m_p / \int_L m(x)dL$, where $m(x)$ is the mass density at a point in the domain. The resonator equation of motion related to the primary system yields

$$m_p \ddot{u}_p(t) + k_p u_p(t) + m_p \ddot{w}(x, p, t) = 0 \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad (1)$$

where $w(x, p, t)$ is the displacement of a point with position vector p related to the cable (primary system), k_p , m_p , u_p are, respectively, the stiffness, mass, and resonator displacement. The relative displacement expressed by $u_p = (u_p - w_{x_p})$, represents the displacement of each resonator p^{th} with respect to the relative displacement of the principal structure (w_{x_p}). Assume there are S undamped spring-mass absorbers attached to the cable at locations x_p , and relative displacements u_p . A representative schematic showing a locally resonant cable is shown in Fig.1. Therefore, by neglecting the displacement of the primary system in Eq. 1 the calculation of the tuned frequency of each resonator is expressed as

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{k_p}{m_p}} \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad (2)$$

Graded metamaterials are structures that host resonating units whereby the natural frequency of the attachments is a smooth and gradually varying function of space. This feature is responsible for the spatial separation of the modes upon varying frequencies and is associated with a position-dependent decrease in the group/phase speed. The frequency grading patterns for the single resonator follow the work of Alshaqqa and Erturk [77], such that

$$\omega_{p,\tau} = \omega_p + \Delta\omega_p - 2\Delta\omega_p \left(\frac{\tau - 1}{S - 1} \right)^d \quad (3)$$

where ω_p is the resonator target frequency around which gradual variation frequencies operate, τ goes from 1 to S , and $2\Delta\omega_p$ defines the range of the frequency grading pattern. For a positive $\Delta\omega_p$, the frequency grading results in a descending pattern, and negative $\Delta\omega_p$ yields in an ascending frequency grading. The power d , which can assume fractional, first-order and high-order, defines the frequency grading profile between the first and last operating frequencies. In this paper, we assume a first-order grading pattern so that $d = 1$, and the graded mass assumes $m_{p,\tau} = k_p/\omega_{p,\tau}$.

The control in multiple resonate frequencies and multiple periodic arrays can be considered by attaching local resonators with multiple degrees of freedom (\bar{n} -DOF) to the principal structure [48, 47]. Hence, for multiple The equations of motion for the \bar{n} -resonators are expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} m_p^{(1)} \ddot{u}_p^{(1)}(t) + k_p^{(1)} u_p^{(1)}(t) + m_p \ddot{w}(x, p, t) &= 0 \\ m_p^{(2)} \ddot{u}_p^{(2)}(t) + k_p^{(2)} [u_p^{(2)}(t) - u_p^{(1)}(t)] + k_p^{(3)} [u_p^{(3)}(t) - u_p^{(2)}(t)] &= 0 \\ &\vdots \\ m_p^{(\bar{n})} \ddot{u}_p^{(\bar{n})}(t) + k_p^{(\bar{n})} [u_p^{(\bar{n})}(t) - u_p^{(\bar{n}-1)}(t)] &= 0 \quad p = 1, 2, \dots, S, \quad \bar{n} = 1, 2, \dots, \bar{N} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $k_p^{\bar{n}}$, $m_p^{\bar{n}}$, and $u_p^{\bar{n}}(t)$ are, respectively, the stiffness, mass, and displacement of the p^{th} resonator at \bar{n} -DOF, \bar{N} is the total number of degree of freedom of each multi-resonator, and the tuned frequency of each resonator is calculated by

$$\omega_p^{\bar{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{k_p^{\bar{n}}}{m_p^{\bar{n}}}} \quad \bar{n} = 1, 2, \dots, \bar{N} \quad (5)$$

The hysteretic damping was assumed on the resonator's springs because this damping model is usually associated with dry friction appearing inside the material. In this case, the hysteretic damping model of the resonators assumes complex stiffness of the form $k = k(1 + i\eta)$, where η is the hysteretic damping factor.

Figure 1: A schematic of a locally resonant metamaterial cable with simple supported boundary conditions.

3. Metamaterial cable conductor for single and graded locally bandgap formation using modal analysis approach

The cable conductor model available in the literature goes from the simplest mathematical based on the taut strings without bending stiffness to a more complex one, considering a homogeneous elastic beam with constant bending stiffness subjected to a constant tensile load and damping [58, 59, 60]. A review of the mechanical models of cables was published by Cardou [61] and Spak et al. [62, 63]. The effect of turbulence wind flow on cable was investigated in [64]. Aeolian vibration caused by wind on conductors is characterised by its low amplitude, which varies between 5 and 150 Hz. Under this situation, aerodynamic damping and inter-strand friction among the wires of a typical conductor can influence the cable's dynamic behaviour. The metamaterial cable equation of motion considering aerodynamic damping and the energy dissipation mechanism associated with the inter-strand friction among the wires of a typical conductor [4, 3] yields

$$EI(x) \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} + i\omega \xi I(x) \frac{d^4 w(x)}{dx^4} - T(x) \frac{d^2 w(x)}{dx^2} + i\omega \varphi w(x) - \omega^2 \rho A w(x) - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p u_p(t) \delta(x - x_p) = f(x, t) \quad (6)$$

where x_p is the attachment location of the p^{th} resonator, $\delta(x - x_p)$ is the spatial Dirac delta function, S is the total number of resonators, and $f(x, t)$ is the external force. For notation simplification m is the mass per unit of length, \mathcal{L} is the linear homogeneous stiffness differential operator, and \mathcal{C} the damping components, which are expressed as

$$m = \rho A(x), \quad \mathcal{L} = EI(x) \frac{d^4}{dx^4} - T(x) \frac{d^2}{dx^2}, \quad \mathcal{C} = \varphi + \xi I \frac{d^4}{dx^4}$$

The locally resonant bandgap edge frequencies are derived in closed form by assuming an infinite number of resonators placed on the primary structure. This expression for the bandgap edge frequencies only depends on the resonant frequency of the resonators and the ratio of resonator mass to primary structure mass. The general solution of Eq. (6) is of the form

$$w(x, t) = \sum_{j=1}^N \phi_j(x) y_j(t) \quad (7)$$

for the undamped metamaterial cable, the aerodynamic damping and the energy dissipation terms are neglected. Hence, substituting Eq.(7) into Eq.(6) gives

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \mathcal{L}[\phi_j(x) y_j(t)] + m \sum_{j=1}^N \phi_j(x) \ddot{y}_j(t) - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p u_p(t) \delta(x - x_p) = f(x, t) \quad (8)$$

where($\dot{}$) denotes the time derivative. The normalised mode shape of the plain structures (cable without resonators attached) satisfies the orthogonality condition [19],

$$\begin{aligned}\int_0^L m\phi_j(x)\phi_i(x)dx &= \delta_{ij} = 1 \\ \int_0^L \mathcal{L}[\phi_j(x)]\phi_i(x)dx &= \omega_j^2\delta_{ij}\end{aligned}$$

where $\phi_j(x)$ and $\phi_i(x)$ are the j -th and i -th normalised mode shapes of the primary structure, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, and ω_j^2 is the natural frequency of the j -th mode of the primary structure. Multiplying Eq. (8) by $\phi_i(x)$ and applying the orthogonality conditions of the mode shapes give

$$\ddot{y}_j(t) + \omega_j^2 y_j(t) - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p u_p(t) \phi_j(x_p) = q_j(t) \quad (9)$$

where $q_j(t) = \int_0^L \phi_i(x) f(x, t) dx$. Assuming $y_j(t) = Y_j e^{i\Omega t}$, $u_p(t) = U_p e^{i\Omega t}$, $f(x, t) = F \delta(x - x_p) e^{i\Omega t}$, $Q_j = F \phi_j(x_e)$, and substituting those variables in Eq. (9) yields

$$(\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2) Y_j - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p U_p \phi_j(x_p) = Q_j \quad (10)$$

with the general solution in Eq. (1), one has

$$-\Omega^2 m_p U_p + k_p U_p - \Omega^2 m_p \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_i = 0 \quad (11)$$

and

$$U_p = \frac{\Omega^2 m_p}{k_p - \Omega^2 m_p} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_i \quad (12)$$

Replacing Eq. (12) in (10), one expresses the metamaterial cable in a modal base as

$$(\omega_i^2 - \Omega^2) Y_j - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p \phi_j(x_p) \frac{\Omega^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_i = Q_j \quad (13)$$

therefore Eq. (10) becomes

$$(\omega_i^2 - \Omega^2) Y_j - \sum_{p=1}^S -\epsilon m \Delta L \omega_p^2 \phi_j(x_p) \frac{\Omega^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_i = Q_j \quad (14)$$

rearranging Eq.(14) yields a system equation of N coupled linear equations that cannot be solved for a simple analytical expression due to the coupling introduced by resonators[23]. This case requires a numerical solution for the response of a given system.

$$(\omega_i^2 - \Omega^2) Y_j - \epsilon \Omega^2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \left(\sum_{p=1}^S m \phi_j(x_p) \phi_i(x_p) \Delta L \right) Y_i = Q_j \quad (15)$$

A simplification proposed by Sugino et al.[23] of the system given in Eq. (15) relies on the consideration that $S \rightarrow \infty$ while mass ratio ϵ is kept unchanged. The domain region becomes infinitesimal, and the resonators scatter throughout the entire domain so that

$$\lim_{S \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{p=1}^S m \phi_j(x_p) \phi_i(x_p) \Delta L \approx \int_0^L m \phi_j(x) \phi_i(x) dx = \delta_{ij} \quad (16)$$

Hence, the simplification proposed in Eq. (16) is exact when $S \rightarrow \infty$, but can be used as a good approximations considering

$$\sum_{p=1}^S m_j \phi_j(x_p) \phi_i(x_p) \approx \epsilon \int_0^L m \phi_j(x) \phi_i(x) dx = \epsilon \delta_{ij} \quad (17)$$

this approximation is crucial for bandgap formation with a finite number of resonators, which become continuous in space with the assumption. Therefore, the limits established in Eq. (17), Eq. (15) one obtains

$$\left((\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2) - \epsilon \Omega^2 \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \right) Y_j = Q_j \quad (18)$$

and the modal displacement, Y_j in closed-form expression z

$$Y_j = \frac{Q_j}{\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \epsilon \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \right)} \quad (19)$$

The system of decoupled equations returns the metamaterial cable transfer receptance in a closed form as

$$\alpha_{re}(\Omega) = \frac{w(x_r, \Omega)}{f(x_e, \Omega)} = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\phi_j(x_r) \phi_j(x_e)}{\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \epsilon \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \right)} \quad (20)$$

where $\alpha_{re}(\omega)$ is a transfer receptance, x_e indicates the location of force application, and x_r the response. The force is a harmonic of unit magnitude and frequency Ω . For the graded metamaterial cable, the tuned frequencies of the absorbers (ω_p) are assumed to be the graded frequencies ($\omega_{p,t}$) as presented in Eq. (3).

3.1. Viscously damped systems

The general equations of motion of a viscously damped system representation rely on the expression $M\ddot{w}(t) + C\dot{w}(t) + Kw(t) = f(t)$. Assuming the general solution of eq. (7), pre-multiplying equation eq. (8) by ϕ_i^T and using the orthogonality properties, equations of motion of a damped system in the modal coordinates with attached resonators may be obtained as [75]

$$\ddot{y}_j(t) + \mathcal{C}\dot{y}_j(t) + \omega_j^2 y_j(t) - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p u_p(t) \phi_j(x_p) = q_j(t) \quad (21)$$

by assuming proportional damping, which implies the \mathcal{C} is simultaneously related to the mass and stiffness, allows us to analyse the damped systems easily as the undamped. Hence, introducing the modal damping ratio ζ_j and substituting in eq.(21), we obtain the modal equations for cable-damped vibrations in the form

$$\ddot{y}_j(t) + 2\zeta_j \omega_j \dot{y}_j(t) + \omega_j^2 y_j(t) - \sum_{p=1}^S k_p u_p(t) \phi_j(x_p) = q_j(t) \quad (22)$$

thereby each of the modal equations on Eq. (22) resembles the one-degree-of-freedom [74]. Since the modal equations are uncoupled, each of them can be solved independently as

$$Y_j = \frac{Q_j}{\omega_j^2 + i2\zeta_j \omega_j \omega - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \epsilon \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2} \right)} \quad (23)$$

and then reassembled through modal transfer receptance for proportional damping is expressed by Eqs.(24) or (34). For the damped system, the transfer receptance for proportional damping is

$$\alpha_{re}(\Omega) = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\phi_j(x_r)\phi_j(x_e)}{\omega_j^2 + i2\zeta_j\omega_j\Omega - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \epsilon \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_p^2 - \Omega^2}\right)} \quad (24)$$

where the viscously damping term is $\zeta_j = (\varphi/\omega_j + \xi I\omega_j)$. For a simply supported cable under axial force, the natural frequency and modal shape can be written as [73]

$$\omega_j = \frac{\pi^2}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A} \left(n^4 + \frac{n^2 TL^2}{\pi^2 EI}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad \phi_j = \sin(j\pi x/L) \quad j = 1, 2, \dots$$

where ρA is the mass per unit of length, EI is the uniform bending rigidity, L is the cable length, and T is the tensile load.

4. Metamaterial cable conductor for multiple locally bandwidth of bandgap formation using modal analysis approach

Adverse conditions can impact a cable's dynamic feature during its lifetime. In such a situation, the typical controls, such as Stockbridge, operating in a specifically tuned frequency loosens its efficiency within the control. Therefore, with proper tuning of the frequency spacing between the local resonators, the bandwidth can increase drastically compared to conventional controls. This section presents the formulation of metamaterial cable for multiple frequencies to induce multiple bandgaps and the graded metamaterial with graded frequency variation to enlarge the bandgap. The general equation of motion for the undamped cable attached to multiple periodic arrays of resonators is of the form

$$\mathcal{L}[w(x, t)] + m\ddot{w}(x, t) - \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \sum_{p=1}^S k_p^{\bar{n}} u_p^{\bar{n}}(t) \delta(x - x_p) = f(x, t) \quad (25)$$

where $\mathcal{L}[w(x, t)]$ is the stiffness operator, $\delta(x - x_p)$ is the Dirac delta function, and $w(x, p, t)$ is the displacement of a point with position vector p , m is the main structure mass, and \bar{N} is the total number of degree of freedom of each multi-resonator. Similar assumptions made in section 3 are validated here, and the general solution presented in Eq. (7) into Eq.(25) gives

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \mathcal{L}[\phi_j(x)] y_j(t) + m \sum_{j=1}^N \phi_j(x) \ddot{y}_j(t) - \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \sum_{p=1}^S k_p^{\bar{n}} u_p^{\bar{n}}(t) \delta(x - x_p) = f(x, t) \quad (26)$$

By multiplying Eq. (26) by the normalised mode shapes $\phi_i(x)$ and applying the orthogonality conditions, the equation of motion became

$$\ddot{y}_j(t) + \omega_j^2 y_j(t) - \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \sum_{p=1}^S k_p^{\bar{n}} u_p^{\bar{n}}(t) \phi_j(x_p) = q_j(t) \quad (27)$$

As expressed in section 3, $y_j(t)$ and $u_p(t)$ assume harmonica solution, and the force $q_j(t)$ in a modal form is $Q_j = F\phi_j(x_e)$. Substituting those modal components in Eq. (27) yields

$$(\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2) Y_j - \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \sum_{p=1}^S k_p^{\bar{n}} U_p^{\bar{n}} \phi_j(x_p) = Q_j \quad (28)$$

the multiple resonators' general solution (Eq. 4) in a modal basis will be

$$- \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \Omega^2 m_p^{\bar{n}} U_p^{\bar{n}} + k_p^{\bar{n}} U_p^{\bar{n}} - \Omega^2 m_p^{\bar{n}} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_j = 0 \quad (29)$$

and the modal displacement of the form

$$U_p^{\bar{n}} = \frac{\Omega^2 m_p^{\bar{n}}}{k_p^{\bar{n}} - \Omega^2 m_p^{\bar{n}}} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_j \quad (30)$$

Substituting Eq. (30) into (28), one obtains the multiples resonators attached to the cable in a modal base solution it has,

$$(\omega_i^2 - \Omega^2) Y_j - \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \sum_{p=1}^S k_p^{\bar{n}} \phi_j(x_p) \frac{\Omega^2}{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2 - \Omega^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x_p) Y_j = Q_j \quad (31)$$

Assuming similar arrangement, simplification, and orthogonality properties described from Eq (13) to (17), the displacement yields

$$Y_j = \frac{Q_j}{\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \epsilon^{\bar{n}} \frac{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2}{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2 - \Omega^2} \right)} \quad (32)$$

The system of decoupled equations returns the multi-frequency metamaterial cable transfer receptance as

$$\alpha_{re}(\Omega) = \frac{w(x_r, \omega)}{f(x_e, \omega)} = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\phi_j(x_r) \phi_j(x_e)}{\omega_j^2 - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \epsilon^{\bar{n}} \frac{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2}{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2 - \Omega^2} \right)} \quad (33)$$

and the receptance in case of the proportional viscous damping will be

$$\alpha_{re}(\Omega) = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\phi_j(x_r) \phi_j(x_e)}{\omega_j^2 + i2\zeta_j \omega_j \Omega - \Omega^2 \left(1 + \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^{\bar{N}} \epsilon^{\bar{n}} \frac{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2}{(\omega_p^{\bar{n}})^2 - \Omega^2} \right)} \quad (34)$$

where x_e indicates the location of force application, x_r the response, and ζ_j is the damping ratio. For the graded metamaterial cable, a spatial frequency variation is assumed. It implies that single or multiple resonators operate in neighbouring frequencies of the target one expressed in Eq. (3) to enlarge the bandgap.

5. Results and discussion

The overhead transmission cable typically consists of a composite structure of different materials and intertwined wires, which can be quite slender and extend over lengths exceeding 100 meters. To establish the reliability of the methodology employed, we compared the experimental dataset of the cable conductor without any controls and the numerical model of the plain or bare cable. Once this paper aims to propose a control mechanism utilising the concept of metastructures, it is important to note that, to date, a physical cable metastructure is not available in our laboratory, nor is there any existing literature on the topic. Therefore, we have utilised a validated and calibrated plain cable model as a reference guide for designing metamaterial cables to control undesired vibration. Furthermore, the validated model of the plain cable serves as a benchmark for creating a control system centred around metamaterial cables.

The physical cable consists of ACSR Grosbeak simply supported with a nominal diameter of $D = 25.15$ mm and a length of $L = 51.950$ m. The dynamic data-driven of the cable without control was experimented with at the laboratory span of the Electric Power Research Center (CEPEL). The experimental plain cable data-driven shown in Figs. 2a and 2b have as input setup a tensile load of 1680 kgf, about 19% of the Grosbeak rated tensile strength (RTS), percentages commonly employed in the application field. The Grosbeak cable was excited by an electrodynamic shaker

at 1.606 m from the support and measured with four accelerometers nominated Ac4, Ac1, Ac2, and Ac3, placed at 1.606 m, 26 m, 34 m, and 39 m, respectively. The electrodynamic shaker was manufactured by Data Physics, model S-150, with controller DP-V150 and amplifier A-10C-05. The maximum velocity is 1.5 m/s; the maximum acceleration is 72 g; the nominal forces are 1000 N, 650 N and 1300 N, respectively, for sinusoidal, random and shock; and the frequency range is 2 Hz to 5 kHz. The amplifier's power is 1250 W; the maximum shaker displacement is 25.4 mm peak-to-peak. The force transducer is a Bruel & Kjaer-model 8230-002 with a nominal sensitivity of 2.41 mV/N. The accelerometers were IEPE Bruel & Kjaer-model Deltatron 4519-001 with 1 gr mass [4, 3]. The force transducer and the three accelerometers are IEPE; their frequency ranges encompass 5 Hz to 6 kHz, according to the manufacturer's specification. The PULSE acquisition data system from Bruel and Kjaer acquired and processed the desired frequency response functions. The frequency range from 5 to 18 Hz is a common range expected for aeolian vibrations in the field [4]. The FRFs are measured with 801 equally spaced frequency points to capture the conductor's closely spaced natural frequencies and obtain well-defined peaks in the FRFs. The time-domain acceleration data are also measured for band-limited white noise and sine sweep excitation, with a frequency band between 5-30 Hz, a time span of 0 to 15 seconds, and a sampling frequency of 256 Hz.

The ACSR Grosbeak cable has a mass per unit length of $\rho A = 1.3027$ kg/m, estimated Young's Modulus expected value of $E = 2.01$ GPa, and density expected value of $\rho = 3000$ kg/m³, as given in Appendix A. The damping coefficients of the physical cable were given in [4, 65] and adopted in the analysis. The equivalent aerodynamic damping coefficient is $\varphi = 0.18$, and inter-strand friction related to a material damping factor is $\xi = 10^{-4}$. A hysteretic damping of $\eta = 0.01$ is imposed in the resonator's spring.

Figure 2: Plain cable experimental set-up: (a) general overview of the CEPEL’s laboratory span and (b) schematic experimental set-up(right) [4, 3]; (c) Comparison of experimental inertance response for numerical response calculated using SEM and Modal Analysis; (d) Inertance response are obtained at accelerometer Ac3 (LHS) and at the point of the accelerometer Ac4 (RHS).

Figures 2c and 2d are the comparison of data-driven inertance response of the cable obtained on accelerometers Ac3 and Ac4, numerically simulated responses using modal analysis and spectral element method (SEM) presented in [67, 66, 3]. Both numerical models assumed the inferred physical parameters in Appendix A. The inertances obtained with SEM are also used to validate the results from the modal analysis simulated inertances. The numerical models (SEM and Modal) that did not consider any damping present sharp resonance peaks, and the curves show a good approximation in a whole frequency band. The cable’s damped model decreases resonance amplitudes and conserves the modal characteristic following the experimental curves. We assumed that our cable numerical model carries the physical entity’s dynamic characteristics from this point. Further, the vibration control designed solutions using metamaterial concepts are evaluated. Hence, this study examines how local bandgap can reduce the vibration of an overhead transmission cable conductor in broadband. We explore three different metamaterial designs: the cable metamaterial single degree of freedom resonator (single-DOF) of Fig. 3a, which is a cable with periodic attached single DOF spring-mass resonator; the cable metamaterial multiple degrees of freedom resonators (multiple-DOF) shown in Fig. 3b. It is a cable with periodic attached multiple DOF spring-mass resonator, and that cable graded metamaterial illustrated in Fig. 3c, which is a cable attached to a gradation in the attached mass of the resonators in the unit cell. The spring coefficient of each resonator and the position are assumed to be the same, whereas the mass of each resonator changes gradually following the resonator’s natural frequency specified in Eq. (3).

Figure 3: Representation of metamaterial cable designed to mitigate vibration: (a) cable with periodic attached single DOF spring-mass resonator, (b) cable attached to a gradation in the attached mass of the unit cell, and (c) cable with periodic attached multiple DOF spring-mass resonator.

5.1. Dispersion curves

Designed controls operate at the tuned resonant frequencies of 9.51 and 15.48 Hz. The resonators are attached uniformly along the cable, resulting in a total of 30% of mass ratio. In an attempt to explain the bandgap formation, dispersion curves are explored in this section. The real and imaginary parts of the wavenumbers $k(\omega)$ estimated using the STMM (briefly described in Appendix B) are plotted in Fig. 4 for the three cable metamaterials to enhance the insight into the band formation. Because of the intricate dependence of the STMM complex on frequency, the eigenproblem $\omega = \omega(k)$ cannot be attained; instead, only an eigenproblem in the form of $k = k(\omega)$ can be formulated. Figs.4a and 4d show the real and imaginary dispersion curve or wavenumber ($k(\omega)$) of the cable metamaterial with single-DOF resonators, operating at frequencies 9.41 Hz and 15.48 Hz, respectively. The attenuation bandgap features a tightly focused frequency gap, with an additional fragmented attenuation band emerging near 11 Hz. The imaginary segment of the wavenumber centred around the designated frequencies (highlighted by black lines in Fig. 4) points to the rapid attenuation of evanescent waves within that frequency range.

Furthermore, the wave propagation behaviour within the pass bands is predominantly governed by purely imaginary propagation constants, dictating the dispersion relations of uninhibitedly propagating waves [25]. In the real portion of the wavenumber, deviations are observable at locally resonant bandgap locations, as illustrated in the figure. Along this trajectory, derivatives concerning $k(\omega)$ showcase negative and nearly zero group velocities within the bandgap. The attenuation characteristics showcased in the dispersion diagram corroborate those anticipated by the receptance curves shown in Fig. 6. The Bragg bandgap is estimated to appear at 24.05Hz when the spacing between resonators is half the wavelength, assuming there are enough unit cells. Although the interaction of the locally resonant and Bragg bandgaps adds complexity, it is not the focus of this paper (for a detailed investigation, see [25]). Additionally, Sugion et al.[26] demonstrated that the Bragg bandgap and locally resonant bandgap do not interact in finite structures because the Bragg bandgap occurs at a much higher frequency, requiring a larger number of unit cells. Using locally resonant components allows for the creation of local low-frequency bandgaps, which is necessary for our application

case.

Figs. 4b and 4e illustrate the real and imaginary wavenumbers of the cable metamaterial with multiple degrees of freedom resonators (multi-DOF) centred at frequencies 9.41 Hz and 15.48 Hz. The findings highlight notable enhancements achieved through integrating multi-DOF resonators, resulting in a widened gap bandwidth of 1.63 and 3.38, as opposed to 1.31 and 0.78 observed in the single-DOF configuration, respectively, for the corresponding frequencies. Here, the bandwidth is the difference between the frequency on the right (f_r) and left (f_l) of the open bandgap, so that $\Delta\omega = f_r - f_l$. Moving on to Figs. 4c and 4f, the real and imaginary wavenumbers of the cable-graded metamaterial are displayed for both target frequencies. Here, the varying bandwidth is attributed to the graded distribution of resonating mass. This configuration yields a significantly expanded attenuation band, showcasing the most remarkable gap bandwidth of 2.88 at the central frequency of 9.41 Hz and an even broader 6.13 at 15.48 Hz. The strategic mass gradation emerges as the optimal approach for effectively enhancing broadband control. At frequencies near the resonator's target frequency, the dispersion curve exhibits a sharp curvature, facilitating the tunability of group velocities at specific frequencies. The group velocity can be calculated as $Cg = d\omega/dk$ m/s and tends to zero inside the bandgap. Through spatial manipulation of the target frequency, it becomes spatially variable, inducing controlled disorder within the medium, coping with the findings in [77, 76, 82, 83]. The group velocity for the cable metamaterials single-DOF resonators tuned at frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz is shown respectively in Figs. 5a and 5d. For the metamaterial multiple-DOF resonators operating at frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz in Figs. 5b and 5e, and for the graded metamaterial in Figs. 5c and 5f.

Figure 4: Dispersion diagram of the cable metamaterials to illustrate the band structure attached with a-d) single-DOF resonators tuned at frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz, respectively; b-e) metamaterial multiple-DOF resonators operating at frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz; and c) graded resonators around the frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz. The graded metamaterial assumes 11 graded units in a representative lattice and similar spacing between them. The orange-shaded region shows the attenuation band, and the black lines are the resonators' natural frequencies (target frequency).

Figure 5: Group velocity versus frequency band of the cable metamaterials: a-d) single-DOF resonators tuned at frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz, respectively; b-e) metamaterial multiple-DOF resonators operating at frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz; and c) graded resonators around the frequencies 9.41 and 15.48 Hz.

5.2. Dynamic response

The concept of bandgap formation through wave-type arguments assumes that there are no standing waves since the structure comprises infinite repeated unit cells and travelling waves. However, in finite systems, the dynamic response is influenced by the mode shapes of the structure. This research assumes the modal analysis method for studying bandgap formation in finite metamaterial cables as dimensional waveguides with local resonance, formulated in sections 3 and 4.

The frequency response function estimation assumes a unitary excitation force is located at the right edge (interface point-0), and the receptance responses estimated along the cable's interface are guided by the points from 0 to 10 of Fig. 3. Figure 6 compares controls performed by attaching the resonators in a periodic and graded arrangement, where the locally resonant bandgaps are presented in both cases. The bandgap region is the frequency band no elastic wave can propagate in the periodic structures. Such a unique property works as a vibration isolator. In the graded arrangement, the rainbow trapping phenomena induce wave confinement due to a spatial wave velocity variation, which also obstructs wave propagation. The single-DOF resonator usually opens a narrow gap, making it impractical to design mechanical filters that are effective against broadband excitation, which demands a more efficient control design. The multiple-DOF resonator and the graded design are alternatives to the single-DOF control.

Figure 6: Comparison among plain, metamaterial single-DOF, metamaterial multiple-DOF, and graded metamaterial cable's numerical receptance responses obtained at accelerometers Ac3 location: (a) metamaterials cable with designed local resonators bandgap at 9.51 Hz, and (b) at 15.48 Hz.

Figure 6a and 6b show the results of the controls designed to operate at 9.51 Hz and 15.48 Hz, respectively. Acoustic metamaterial relies on the infinite-resonator concept that considers the simple bandgap expression occurs exactly when $S \rightarrow \infty$. However, in practical applications, S will assume a finite number. The mass ratio directly affects the attenuation bandwidth, which saturates and cannot be widened by increasing the mass (set as 30% of plain cable mass). In comparing the receptance response for the plain cable, the metamaterial cable with single-DOF resonator, metamaterial cable with multiple-DOF resonator, and graded metamaterial, the results found that the graded metamaterial can produce a wider bandgap than the counterpart of the other case. All metamaterial configurations achieved local control. Local modes inside the local resonant bandgap emerge in the multiple-DOF case because of energy localisation due to the attached resonators and the absence of damping in this analysis.

The receptance response is also estimated along with the controlled cable's interface (points 0-10 of fig. 3) with

unitary excitation force located at point 10. Figure 7a shows the receptance responses heatmap of the cable without control obtained over its interface. The red marks on the heatmap represent the highest amplitude of each mode resonance peak, and the blueish area is the valley representing anti-resonance or the bandwidth gap. Figure 7b and 7e are the single-DOF resonator metamaterial cable receptance heatmaps vibration controlled at 9.51 and 15.48Hz, respectively. Figures 7c and 7f are the multiple-DOF resonators metamaterial cable receptance heatmaps, Figs 7c and 7f the graded metamaterial, where the vibration is controlled at similar frequencies of the single-DOF metamaterial. In those cases, the local resonant bandgap opens at similar resonators' tuned frequencies and remains along the heatmaps. Comparing the metamaterials heatmap responses, the gain in bandwidth and valley amplitude of the graded configuration is evident. Those results reinforce the metamaterials' efficiency in mitigating vibration in the required band frequency by forming a local resonant bandgap. One can also see the shifting resonance frequencies towards the neighbourhood modes around the opening bandgap. The bandgap attenuating and isolating vibration in a frequency region also induces other resonance frequencies near the isolating frequency band region. Therefore, a common problem induced by vibration control based on dynamic resonators can be manipulated in some frequency range with the graded metamaterial. The bandgap local mode shape emerging in the multiple-DOF metamaterial is seen on the heatmap, which can be attenuated by imposing some damping in the resonators.

Figure 7: Receptance heatmaps depicting the contours of cable length versus excitation frequency for (a) Plain cable, (b) periodic single-DOF metamaterial cable designed locally bandgap at 9.51 Hz, (c) periodic multiple-DOF metamaterial cable designed locally bandgap at 9.51 Hz, and (d) graded metamaterial cable designed locally bandgap at 9.51 Hz, (e) single-DOF metamaterial cable designed locally bandgap at 15.48 Hz, (f) multiple-DOF metamaterial cable designed locally bandgap at 15.48 Hz, and (g) graded metamaterial cable designed locally bandgap at 15.48 Hz.

5.2.1. Damping effect

Typically, the dynamic resonator is designed to operate at a determined frequency. The dynamic coupling between resonators and the primary structure (cable) causes a split on the controlled resonant peak, introducing additional degrees of freedom around the target mode shape. Thereby, other resonance frequencies appear on the left and the right of the operating frequency of the primary system being controlled by the resonators. This passive vibration control has a well-defined working range and, when out of this frequency range, may cause highly undesired behaviour, such as an increase in the amplitude of adjacent modes. A few resonances after and before the bandgap increase in amplitude for the metamaterials cable, and other mode shapes in minor amplitude arise around the gap. The locally resonant bandgap targets the modal neighbourhood and occurs when an infinite number of resonators are placed on the structure. Each mode shape from the plain structure has two associated resonant frequencies, one below the bandgap frequency range and one above. These resonances correspond to different mode shapes of the structure with resonators, one where the primary structure is in phase with the resonators and one where it is out of phase. The

neighbourhood modes are targeted by the locally resonant bandgap with the central frequency shift. The interaction of those neighbouring modes is not the focus of this paper (see e.g. [26] for detailed discussion). Despite the multiple-DOF metamaterial widening attenuation bandwidth at the target frequency, localised vibration modes are observed inside the local bandgap in which vibration energy is confined over some specific spatial region along the cable. In the analysis, the cable’s model aerodynamic damping and inter-strand friction among the wires of a conductor are included, as in Eq. (6). The parameters of the aerodynamic damping coefficient, inter-strand friction related to a material damping factor, and hysteretic damping in the resonator’s spring are described in sections 3 and 4.

Figure 8: Comparison among plain, metamaterial single-DOF, metamaterial multiple-DOF, and graded metamaterial cable’s receptance responses considering no damping, damping only in the cable, damping in cable and resonator: (a) Single-DOF metamaterial cable operates at 9.51 Hz, (b) multiple-DOF metamaterial cable operates at 9.51 Hz, (c) graded metamaterial cable operates at 9.51 Hz, (d) Single-DOF metamaterial cable operates at 15.48 Hz, (e) multiple-DOF metamaterial cable operates at 15.48 Hz, (f) graded metamaterial cable operates at 15.48 Hz.

The shift of resonant peaks, amplitude amplification towards neighbouring modes, and localized vibration modes within the bandgap are common issues in metamaterials dynamic response. These problems can be mitigated by introducing damping into the system. In [69, 71], the authors explored the mechanics of metadamping using dissipative metamaterials. In contrast, Hu et al. [41] and Thomes et al. [68] reduced localised vibration modes by incorporating damping into the resonators. Aladwani and Nouh [70] investigate the frequency and damping ratio band structures in finite beam metastructure, assuming damping into the host medium and in resonators. In the present study, the cable’s model assumes structural damping, including aerodynamic and material damping, and the damping associated with the resonator’s spring. Therefore, we investigate the effect of damping on the receptance response due to a unitary excitation and multi-frequency parametric excitation.

Figure 8a and 8d show the receptance response of damped plain cable (blue line), undamped single-DOF metamaterial cable (orange line), damped single-DOF metamaterial cable without resonators damping (yellow line), damped single-DOF metamaterial cable with $\eta = 5\%$ of hysteretic damping in the resonators (purple line), and damped single-DOF metamaterial cable with $\eta = 10\%$ of damping in the resonators (purple line). For all cases, the metamaterial’s

cable displacement is estimated for a transverse harmonic 1 N force applied at the right end (point 10). The presence of damping only on the primary system (cable) due to the aerodynamic and material damping mainly induces spatial attenuation on the cable’s modal shape. It barely affects adjacent modes induced by the resonators and the bandgap intern modes. This spatial amplitude attenuation is seen through the resonating peaks of the receptance response (yellow curve). For higher structural damping levels of the primary system, the effectiveness of the local resonance band gap drops as a trade-off, which can impair the effectiveness of the control. By considering damping effects within the cable and the resonators, we reduce the amplitudes of neighbouring and internal bandgap mode shapes. Damping within the resonators influences the intensity of adjacent peaks generated by the open gap and the internal modes. As the damping factor increases, there is an observable decrease in the amplitude of all resonating peaks, indicating spatial attenuation. This trend is supported by the receptance FRFs, which affirm that higher levels of damping within the resonators lead to notable attenuation within the bandgap region. This, in turn, introduces localized alterations in the dynamic response near the targeted resonant frequency. A minor impact on the cable’s mode shape is observed, primarily influenced by the dominant structural damping. These findings are consistent with those presented in [70].

Figures 8b and 8e show the multiple-DOF metamaterial receptance responses and Figs 8c and 8f the graded metamaterial. Likewise, for the single-DOF metamaterial cable, by considering damping only on the primary system, the resonant peaks decrease in amplitude along the entire frequency band, except for the local resonances caused by the resonators. The combination of both damping mechanisms achieved a reduction in receptance amplitude. The localised vibration mode seen inside the bandgap disappears by the resonator’s damping adding. Overall, the damping in the designed resonator removes the undesired vibration mode from including local resonator modes and improves the attenuation amplitude on adjacent mode shapes close to the local open bandgap.

5.3. *Vibration control performance under the effect of the multi-frequency parametric excitation*

Aeolian vibration is the oscillation induced by the wind on transmission and distribution lines’ conductors and overhead shield wires. This type of motion is one of the major contributors to the damage and fatigue experienced by these components, leading to reduced reliability and serviceability of the lines. Typically, aeolian vibration is characterised by frequency oscillations ranging from 5 to 150 Hz with low amplitude proportional to the conductor’s diameter. The excitation used here is based on the Kaimal spectrum, usually applied to wind modelling, combined with the multi-frequency parametric excitation assumed to range from 8 to 12 Hz with an amplitude of 1N, to comprise the target frequency of 9.51 Hz that the controls were designed to operate. The time-domain input excitation signal is shown in Fig. 9a and the frequency-domain in Fig. 9b.

The auto-spectral density (PSD) of the conductor’s dynamic response to spectral excitation is determined using linear system theory [78]. The time-domain PSD signal is obtained by numerically computing the discretised target signal’s inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT). Excitation frequencies were selected accordingly to include the local open bandgap at a target frequency of 9.51 Hz and the neighbouring resonant frequencies of 8.5 and 11.7 Hz. Figures 10a and 10b illustrate the PSD of the plain and cable metamaterial single-DOF in both frequency and time domains under a broadband excitation. The broadband excitation raises the mode shape amplitude of the controlled and uncontrolled cable at the excitation frequency range. The single-DOF metamaterial attenuates the response in a narrow frequency band that includes the target and slightly in the adjacent frequencies. The time-domain response amplitude reduction is achieved by cable metamaterial single-DOF configuration, quantified in Table 1.

Figure 9: Broadband excitation force ranging from 8 to 12 Hz: (a) Excitation signal in the time domain; (b) Excitation signal in the frequency domain. Excitation.

Frequency and time domain responses of the plain and cable metamaterial multiple-DOF are shown in Figs. 10c and 10d and in Figs. 10e and 10f of the cable graded metamaterial. Cable metamaterial multiple-DOF enlarges the bandwidth covering the target frequency mode shape and the subsequent vibration mode, while the graded metamaterial embraces the next two mode shapes. By assuming damping in the resonators, the mode shapes covered by the bandgaps increase in three modes for the metamaterial multiple-DOF and five modes for the graded. In both cases, the opened local bandgap covers the broadband excitation. However, the graded metamaterial enhances the vibration control, which presents a greater amplitude attenuation on the response.

We use the root mean square (RMS) value of the time signal to quantify the vibration reduction achieved in each metamaterial cable design. The RMS measures the amplitude of the wave time history signal and gives an amplitude value directly related to the energy content. Make the RMS a good metric to quantify the vibration control efficiency. The percentage of vibration attenuation delivery for each control system is estimated by $[(RMS_{pc} - RMS_{mc})/RMS_{pc}] * 100$, where RMS_{pc} is the time signal RMS value for the plain cable, and RMS_{mc} time signal RMS value for the metamaterial cable.

Vibration control	Undamped system [%]	Damping in cable [%]	Damping in cable and resonator [%]
Metamaterial -singleDOF	0	46.68	86.03
Metamaterial - multiple DOF	36.03	60.10	95.41
Graded metamaterial	92.19	96.65	99.63

Table 1: Vibration control level achieved by the single-DOF, multiple-DOF, and graded metamaterial cables, considering various damping scenarios.

We used the root mean square (RMS) value of the time signal to evaluate the effectiveness of each metamaterial cable design in reducing vibration. The RMS measures the amplitude of the wave time history signal and is a good metric for quantifying vibration control efficiency, as it directly relates to the signal energy content. To estimate the percentage of vibration attenuation achieved by each control system, we used the formula $[(RMS_{pc} - RMS_{mc})/RMS_{pc}] * 100$, where RMS_{pc} is the time signal RMS value for the plain cable, and RMS_{mc} is the time signal RMS value for the meta-

Figure 10: Frequency- (left) and time (right)-domain response of metamaterial cable beam at excited by broadband excitation force: (a-b) Single-DOF metamaterial cable, (c-d) multiple-DOF metamaterial cable, and (e-f) graded metamaterial cable.

material cable. Table 1 summarises the vibration control level achieved by the single-DOF, multiple-DOF, and graded metamaterial cables, considering various damping scenarios. Notably, the cable-graded metamaterial performed best, achieving up to 99% broadband vibration reduction when damping was applied to both the cable and the resonator and 92% reduction for the undamped system. The metamaterial multiple-DOF cable performed best in controlling amplitude when damping was applied to the cable and resonator, achieving 95% amplitude reduction and 36% without damping. However, the metamaterial single-DOF cable had lower performance in controlling broadband excitation in this study, achieving 86% reduction with systems damping and no control in vibration amplitude without damping. In practical applications, aerodynamic damping and inter-strand friction will be present in the system. Under these circumstances, the metamaterial cables still achieved good amplitude attenuation, with reduction levels varying from 46 to 96%.

6. Conclusion

This work investigated broadband vibration mitigation employing a metamaterial and graded metamaterial cable conductor used in the overhead transmission application. We calculated the modal analysis theory for bandgap estimation proposed in [26], which was extended to a cable element and presented for a graded and multi-frequency application. When we wished to widen the gap, the concept of graded metamaterial proved a solid alternative. The results show the concept of graded metamaterial through the cable’s receptance responses, and the bandgap heatmap shows the gain when using the graded metamaterial, which influences the bandwidth. For an application study case, we considered a cable metamaterial assuming similar characteristics of a physical cable installed at CEPEL’s laboratory to represent all functional features and links with the working system. The physical cable’s data drive was used to calibrate our numerical model, and the structural parameters were inferred with Bayesian identification theory. The cable metamaterial has shown to be an efficient solution to mitigate vibration in broadband, and a better configuration is the graded arrangement, which was confirmed by the dispersion diagram that explained the bandgap formation. Damping in structure and resonators improves the performance of the metamaterial cables in signal amplitude reduction. Damping associated with the resonator improves the gap bandwidth, reaching 3 to 5 neighbouring mode shapes of the target frequency. Therefore, it is a good choice to assume the metastructure design. Overhead transmission cable conductors are subjected to broadband vibration. Thus, the metamaterial cable copes with the necessity of such broad control. Again, the graded metamaterial cable better performed control in the multi-frequency parametric excitation, in the best configuration reaching up to 99% of vibration reduction.

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Appendix A. Cable parameter assessment using Bayesian inference

The process of building a computational model (\mathcal{M}) is considered to describe the physical system (\mathcal{B}). In addition, a set of measurements (y) is known and the structuring process occurs from the identification of the parameters’ vector of interest (θ). Where y and θ are modelled as a random variable, the model’s predictive response is given by $y^m = y^m(\theta)$. The *a posteriori* probability distribution function(PDF), which relates the PDFs of the experimental data to the vector of parameters of interest $\pi(\theta|y)$, is based on the Bayes theorem expressed in terms of probability distributions, and takes the following form

$$\pi(\theta|y) = \frac{\pi(y|\theta)\pi(\theta)}{\pi(y)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\pi(y|\theta)$ represents the system’s likelihood function, $\pi(\theta)$ *prior* PDF, and $\pi(y)$ is the PDF associated with the experimental data. The information about the likelihood PDF can be obtained using a particular model of observation of the system. It is considered that the relationship between the observed data (y) and the predictions of the ($y(\theta)^m$)

model can be described from an observation model with additive measurement noise. (ν) as $y^{exp} = y(\theta)^m + \nu$. The additive measurement noise. describes the difference between an experimental observation and the prediction of the model, represented by a random vector. Therefore, given that y , θ and ν are random variables will be related to a joint PDF $\pi(y, \theta, \nu)$. By considering that the noise is stationary, Gaussian with known variance σ_ν^2 , then the likelihood function can be represented as

$$\pi(y^{exp}|\theta_i) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} \sigma_\nu^n} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(y^{exp} - y^m(\theta_i))^T (y^{exp} - y^m(\theta_i))}{\sigma_\nu^2}\right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

which corresponds to the probability of having measured data y^{exp} given a specific model $y(\theta)^m$, defined by the parameter set θ . To obtain information about the unknown parameters, we used the Monte Carlo Markov Chain from the UQLab toolbox [72].

The experimental data y^{exp} used for the Bayesian model updating comprise the cable's inertance responses data driven presented in section 5. The unknown parameter vector is defined as $\theta = \{E, \rho\}$, and for the model updating we assumed uniform prior distribution of density and Young's modulus on the intervals $U_\rho(2.8e3, 3.2e3)$ and $U_E(190e9, 210e9)$, respectively. The estimation operates with 20 chains in the MCMC containing 5000 sample each one.

Figure A.11: Density plots of prior (a), posterior distribution with the posterior mean point estimator for each inferred parameter (b); Convergence of the Young's modulus (c) and density (d).

Figures A.11(a-b) are the density plots of prior and posterior distribution related to their respective discrepancy parameter $\pi(\sigma^2)$ of each parameter, with the posterior mean point estimator for each inferred parameter. Figures A.11(c-d) is the convergence graph of the expected parameter values of all chains. Results show that Young's modulus converges to the expected value of $E = 2.01$ GPa and density to the expected value of 3000 kg/m^3 estimated from the experimental data.

Appendix B. Spectral transfer matrix approach and wavenumber estimation

Periodic structures consist of identical unit cells connected end-to-end in periodic arrays. The spectral transfer matrix method (STMM) is derived from the transfer matrix method, where the lattice structures are built with the spectral elements. In STMM, the spectral modelling of the κ th unit-cell is defined by assembling the spectral element models of all cells in the global coordinates as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}_{LL}^*(\omega) & \mathbf{S}_{LR}^*(\omega) \\ \mathbf{S}_{RL}^*(\omega) & \mathbf{S}_{RR}^*(\omega) \end{bmatrix}_{\kappa} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_L(\omega) \\ \mathbf{d}_R(\omega) \end{Bmatrix}_{\kappa} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_L \\ \mathbf{f}_R \end{Bmatrix}_{\kappa} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where \mathbf{d} is the global spectral nodal degrees of freedom (DOFs) vector, and \mathbf{f} is the global spectral nodal forces, $\mathbf{S}^* = S(\omega)$ represents the spectral dynamic stiffness matrix of the substructure κ condensed onto its left and right boundaries of the unit cell, denoted by the subscripts L and R, respectively. This matrix relates external nodal forces/moments to nodal displacements/rotations defined at the left/right cross-sections of the substructure. Equation. (B.1) can be rearranged in the state vectors of the form $\mathbf{u}_R = \mathbf{T}(\omega)\mathbf{u}_L$. In this case, the states are $\mathbf{u}_R^T = [\mathbf{d}_R, \mathbf{f}_R]^T$ and $\mathbf{u}_L^T = [\mathbf{d}_L, \mathbf{f}_L]^T$, and $\mathbf{T}(\omega)$ ($2n \times 2n$) symplectic is the spectral transfer matrix, that in full derivation yields

$$\mathbf{T}(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} -(\mathbf{S}_{LR}^*)^{-1}\mathbf{S}_{LL}^* & -(\mathbf{S}_{LR}^*)^{-1} \\ \mathbf{S}_{RL}^* - \mathbf{S}_{RR}^*(\mathbf{S}_{LR}^*)^{-1}\mathbf{S}_{LL}^* & -\mathbf{S}_{RR}^*(\mathbf{S}_{LR}^*)^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

By using the coupling conditions between two consecutive substructures κ and $\kappa - 1$, so that $\mathbf{u}_L^{(\kappa)} = \mathbf{u}_R^{(\kappa-1)}$, where the state vectors will lead to

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{(\kappa)} = \mathbf{T}(\omega)\mathbf{u}_L^{(\kappa-1)} \quad (\kappa = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Suppose the substructure is a periodic lattice structure with N lattice cells identical. In that case, each lattice cell will have the identical transfer matrix as $\mathbf{T}_1(\omega) = \mathbf{T}_2(\omega) = \dots = \mathbf{T}_N(\omega) = \mathbf{T}(\omega)$. If the substructure corresponds to a periodic structure consisting of N cells identical to the lattice, from Bloch's theorem, Eq. (B.3) can be rewritten as $\mathbf{u}_L^{(\kappa)} = \mu(\omega)\mathbf{u}_L^{(\kappa-1)}$, where its solutions is the wave modes of the global structure $\{(\mu_j, \Phi_j)\}_j$. They are computed using the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathbf{T}\Phi_j = \mu_j\Phi_j, \quad \det(\mathbf{T} - \mu_j\mathbf{I}) = 0 \quad (\text{B.4})$$

In the periodic structure, the transfer matrix is identical for every cell. Therefore, for a given mode j , the propagation constants parameter $\mu_j = e^{-ik_jL}$ characterizes the wavenumber k_j , while Φ_j represents the wave mode shape, that relates the spatial displacements and internal forces over the cross-section. For near-periodic and non-periodic structures that imply the periodicity breaking, an equivalent wavenumber k_n is also defined from the propagation constant $\mu_n = e^{-ik_nL}$ of the finite length metamaterial, derived from the eigenvalue problem [83],

$$\det(\mathbf{T} - \mu_n\mathbf{I}) = 0 \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Appendix B.1. Wavenumber expression of the metamaterial cable

By assuming the general solution of Eq. (6) based on the spectral form $w(x, t) = \hat{w}e^{-ikx}$, and the mass ratio of the resonators' natural frequency, the analytical wavenumber of the cable metamaterial hosting single and graded (Eq.B.6), and multiple (Eq.B.7) configurations of the resonators yields [84],

$$k(\omega) = \pm \left(-\frac{T}{2EI} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{T}{2EI}\right)^2 + \frac{\rho A \omega^2}{EI} \left[1 + \epsilon \frac{1}{1 - (\Omega/\omega_p)^2}\right]} \right)^{1/2} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

and

$$k(\omega) = \pm \left(-\frac{T}{2EI} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{T}{2EI}\right)^2 + \frac{\rho A \omega^2}{EI} \left[1 + \sum_{\bar{n}=1}^N \epsilon_{\bar{n}} \frac{1}{1 - (\Omega/\omega_{p\bar{n}})^2} \right]} \right)^{1/2} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

To validate the dispersion diagrams provided by the STMM model, we conduct a comparison of the wavenumbers against curves obtained through analytical solutions, as detailed in Equations B.6 and B.7 of the paper. Illustrated in Figures B.12a, B.12b, and B.12c are the results for metamaterial cables configured with single-degree-of-freedom (single-DOF) resonators, multi-degree-of-freedom (multi-DOF) resonators, and graded resonators, respectively. Focusing on the target frequency of 9.41 Hz, both the real and imaginary components of the wavenumber demonstrate remarkable agreement between numerical and analytical outcomes within the designed metamaterial structures. Section 5.1 elaborates on the in-depth comprehension of wave propagation and the formation of bandgaps.

Figure B.12: Wavenumber of metamaterial cable operating at the target frequency of 9.41 Hz calculated with STMM (orange line) and analytical expression (blue line). a) single-DOF resonators, b) multiple-DOF resonators, and c) graded resonators.

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